

ЕНЕРГИЕН ФОРУМ 2017

ОЦЕНКА НА ОСТАТЪЧНОТО ЕНЕРГООТДЕЛЯНЕ НА ОТРАБОТЕНО РЕМИКС ГОРИВО

Ивайло Найденов, Калин Филипов

SPENT REMIX FUEL DECAY HEAT EVALUATION

Ivaylo Naydenov, Kalin Filipov

В настоящия анализ е изследвано остатъчното енергоотделяне на четири разновидности на отработени REMIX горива. Анализирани са актинидите с най-голяма специфична мощност на енергоотделянето. Резултатите са сравнени със стойности, получени от предходни анализи на ураново и класическо смесено уран-плутониево (MOX) гориво.

Introduction

Spent fuel's decay heat is an important feature when considering its management. It determines the cooling time before reprocessing or disposal and has an overall impact on fuel cycle's back-end activities. Major contributors are some fission products, minor actinides, and plutonium – their decay heat is listed in Table 1. A comparison of UOX and MOX spent fuel decay heat has been done in [1].

Table 1. Decay heat of main actinide isotopes, W/kg [2-4]

^{241}Am	114.00	^{238}Pu	560.00
$^{242\text{m}}\text{Am}$	4.49	^{239}Pu	1.90
^{243}Am	6.43	^{240}Pu	6.80
^{242}Cm	122 000.00	^{241}Pu	4.20
^{244}Cm	2 830.00	^{242}Pu	0.10
^{245}Cm	5.71	^{237}Np	-

The REMIX fuel concept is a novel approach for closing the fuel cycle using WWER reactor types [5]. The current analysis is focused on various REMIX spent fuel compositions' decay heat generation up to 300 years of cooling. Four REMIX fuel types are examined with their respective compositions presented in [6]. The decay heat generation has been calculated using the ORIGEN module of the SCALE6.1 software package [7]. The results for REMIX spent fuel are compared with the results for UO₂ (TBC-M fuel assembly) and MOX fuel. MOX fuel results are discussed in [1].

Results and discussion

The total decay heat as a function of time (0.1 – 300.0 years of cooling) has been calculated. The results are shown in Table 1. Visual representation is provided on Figure 1. Table 2 represents the contribution of main actinides to spent fuel's decay heat. The evolution of decay heat's components over time for REMIX 1 fuel is shown on Figure 2. The values of decay heat components for all REMIX fuel varieties and their change over time are presented in Table 3.

Table 1. UOX, REMIX, and MOX spent fuel decay heat as a function of cooling time, W/tHM

		0.1	0.3	1.0	3.0	10.0	30.0	100.0	300.0
		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX1	W/tHM	1.63E+05	7.94E+04	2.61E+04	7.80E+03	2.69E+03	1.64E+03	5.75E+02	2.35E+02
REMIX2	W/tHM	1.64E+05	8.06E+04	2.69E+04	8.42E+03	3.23E+03	1.97E+03	6.92E+02	2.72E+02
REMIX3	W/tHM	1.65E+05	8.12E+04	2.73E+04	8.76E+03	3.54E+03	2.19E+03	7.85E+02	3.00E+02
REMIX4	W/tHM	1.65E+05	8.16E+04	2.75E+04	8.95E+03	3.73E+03	2.33E+03	8.61E+02	3.22E+02
UOX (TBC-M)	W/tHM	1.60E+05	7.68E+04	2.40E+04	6.58E+03	1.82E+03	1.14E+03	4.25E+02	1.77E+02
MOX1 W17x17	W/tHM	1.60E+05	8.23E+04	3.13E+04	9.91E+03	3.56E+03	2.29E+03	1.06E+03	6.29E+02

Figure 1. UOX, REMIX, and MOX spent fuel decay heat as a function of cooling time, W/tHM

Table 2. Plutonium's, americium's, and curium's contributions to REMIX spent fuel's decay heat

Fuel type	Element	0.1	0.3	1.0	3.0	10.0	30.0	100.0	300.0
		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	Pu	0.21%	0.43%	1.34%	4.44%	12.23%	17.34%	30.78%	26.47%
	Am	0.01%	0.01%	0.08%	0.54%	3.91%	12.08%	40.21%	72.69%
	Cm	2.40%	4.02%	7.32%	15.48%	33.52%	25.58%	5.06%	0.10%
	Other nucl.	97.39%	95.53%	91.26%	79.54%	50.34%	44.99%	23.95%	0.74%
REMIX 2	Pu	0.31%	0.64%	1.94%	6.14%	15.19%	21.43%	37.25%	29.61%
	Am	0.01%	0.02%	0.09%	0.57%	3.63%	11.11%	36.90%	69.55%
	Cm	3.05%	5.15%	9.59%	20.25%	39.56%	30.14%	5.96%	0.12%
	Other nucl.	96.63%	94.19%	88.38%	73.03%	41.63%	37.31%	19.90%	0.71%
REMIX 3	Pu	0.41%	0.83%	2.48%	7.65%	17.93%	25.01%	41.95%	32.06%
	Am	0.01%	0.02%	0.10%	0.60%	3.54%	10.68%	34.60%	67.12%
	Cm	3.04%	5.11%	9.45%	19.47%	36.07%	27.21%	5.25%	0.11%
	Other nucl.	96.55%	94.04%	87.97%	72.29%	42.46%	37.10%	18.20%	0.71%
REMIX 4	Pu	0.49%	0.99%	2.95%	8.95%	20.35%	28.00%	45.39%	33.93%
	Am	0.01%	0.02%	0.10%	0.61%	3.51%	10.45%	32.95%	65.26%
	Cm	3.48%	5.86%	10.91%	22.37%	40.25%	29.97%	5.63%	0.12%
	Other nucl.	96.03%	93.13%	86.04%	68.07%	35.89%	31.57%	16.03%	0.69%

Figure 2. REMIX 1 decay heat components' change over time, W/tHM

Table 3. REMIX spent fuel decay heat components, W/tHM

Fuel type	Element	0.1	0.3	1.0	3.0	10.0	30.0	100.0	300.0
		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	Pu	3.42E+02	3.45E+02	3.49E+02	3.46E+02	3.29E+02	2.84E+02	1.77E+02	6.21E+01
	Am	9.10E+00	1.16E+01	1.99E+01	4.23E+01	1.05E+02	1.98E+02	2.31E+02	1.71E+02
	Cm	3.89E+03	3.19E+03	1.91E+03	1.21E+03	9.01E+02	4.19E+02	2.91E+01	2.39E-01
	Rest	1.58E+05	7.58E+04	2.38E+04	6.20E+03	1.35E+03	7.37E+02	1.38E+02	1.74E+00
	Total	1.63E+05	7.94E+04	2.61E+04	7.80E+03	2.69E+03	1.64E+03	5.75E+02	2.35E+02
REMIX 2	Pu	5.15E+02	5.18E+02	5.22E+02	5.17E+02	4.91E+02	4.23E+02	2.58E+02	8.04E+01
	Am	1.20E+01	1.46E+01	2.38E+01	4.84E+01	1.17E+02	2.19E+02	2.55E+02	1.89E+02
	Cm	5.00E+03	4.15E+03	2.58E+03	1.71E+03	1.28E+03	5.95E+02	4.12E+01	3.33E-01
	Rest	1.58E+05	7.59E+04	2.37E+04	6.15E+03	1.34E+03	7.36E+02	1.38E+02	1.93E+00
	Total	1.64E+05	8.06E+04	2.69E+04	8.42E+03	3.23E+03	1.97E+03	6.92E+02	2.72E+02
REMIX 3	Pu	6.70E+02	6.73E+02	6.77E+02	6.70E+02	6.35E+02	5.47E+02	3.29E+02	9.60E+01
	Am	1.35E+01	1.64E+01	2.61E+01	5.22E+01	1.25E+02	2.34E+02	2.72E+02	2.01E+02
	Cm	5.00E+03	4.15E+03	2.58E+03	1.71E+03	1.28E+03	5.95E+02	4.12E+01	3.33E-01
	Rest	1.59E+05	7.64E+04	2.40E+04	6.33E+03	1.50E+03	8.11E+02	1.43E+02	2.12E+00
	Total	1.65E+05	8.12E+04	2.73E+04	8.76E+03	3.54E+03	2.19E+03	7.85E+02	3.00E+02
REMIX 4	Pu	8.03E+02	8.06E+02	8.10E+02	8.01E+02	7.59E+02	6.53E+02	3.91E+02	1.09E+02
	Am	1.45E+01	1.74E+01	2.76E+01	5.48E+01	1.31E+02	2.44E+02	2.84E+02	2.10E+02
	Cm	5.75E+03	4.78E+03	3.00E+03	2.00E+03	1.50E+03	6.99E+02	4.84E+01	3.90E-01
	Rest	1.59E+05	7.60E+04	2.36E+04	6.09E+03	1.34E+03	7.36E+02	1.38E+02	2.22E+00
	Total	1.65E+05	8.16E+04	2.75E+04	8.95E+03	3.73E+03	2.33E+03	8.61E+02	3.22E+02

Since the decay heat originates from the energy emitted by decaying unstable nuclides present in the spent fuel, its change over time depends only on those nuclides' decay constants. That's the reason the decay heat due to plutonium, americium, and curium changes in patterns similar to those observed in [1]. There's also a dependence on initial plutonium concentration – the higher the plutonium's concentration, the higher the minor actinides', the higher their contribution to decay heat and the higher the decay heat. Basically, the contribution of all elements other than plutonium, americium, and curium remains the same in all considered REMIX fuels. That can be observed in the results shown in Tables 1 and 2 and on Figure 1. The reason is that with each recycle (each following REMIX fuel) the share of plutonium increases and its isotopic composition deteriorates.

Comparing REMIX fuel with uranium and MOX fuels (Figure 1) becomes clear that REMIX fuel's decay heat is slightly higher than that of uranium fuel which is the expected result. However, after the third and fourth recycles the decay heat is similar to that of MOX fuel. It is worthwhile noting that this levels of decay heat are reached after multiple uranium and plutonium recycles with REMIX fuel while if MOX is used those levels are reached after a single recycle. Moreover, in long-term perspective (after 100 years) the decay heat levels are significantly lower than those of MOX fuel. Concerning the decay heat components' change over time (Figure 2) it follows the same patterns as UOX and MOX do. Those patterns were identified in [1].

Table 4. Total minor actinides' contribution (MA) and total MA and plutonium contribution to decay heat

Fuel type	Element	0.1	0.3	1.0	3.0	10.0	30.0	100.0	300.0
		y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y
REMIX 1	MA	2.40%	4.04%	7.40%	16.02%	37.43%	37.66%	45.27%	72.79%
	MA+Pu	2.61%	4.47%	8.74%	20.46%	49.66%	55.01%	76.05%	99.26%
REMIX 2	MA	3.06%	5.17%	9.68%	20.83%	43.19%	41.25%	42.86%	69.67%
	MA+Pu	3.37%	5.81%	11.62%	26.97%	58.37%	62.69%	80.10%	99.29%
REMIX 3	MA	3.04%	5.13%	9.55%	20.06%	39.61%	37.89%	39.85%	67.23%
	MA+Pu	3.45%	5.96%	12.03%	27.71%	57.54%	62.90%	81.80%	99.29%
REMIX 4	MA	3.49%	5.88%	11.01%	22.98%	43.76%	40.43%	38.58%	65.38%
	MA+Pu	3.97%	6.87%	13.96%	31.93%	64.11%	68.43%	83.97%	99.31%

Table 4 shows the total contributions of minor actinides (MA) and minor actinides and plutonium to the total decay heat. Once again the results position the REMIX fuel between uranium and MOX fuel. It is valuable to remark that the contribution of minor actinides decreases over multiple recycles.

Conclusion

REMIX fuel operation allows for multiple fissile material recycling while keeping spent fuel's decay heat under the values set by single recycle using MOX fuel. Given that fission products and minor actinides are to be separated and vitrified after several years of cooling (usually after 10), this novel concept would allow fuel cycle closure that is more beneficial than classic MOX fuel usage in terms of spent fuel's decay heat.

References:

1. Naydenov I., K. Filipov, Impact of fresh fuel type and cooling time on PWR spent nuclear fuel's decay heat, *In: Proceedings of the XXI Scientific conference of the FPEPM 2016 Vol. 1*, Sozopol, Bulgaria, pp. 96-101, 2016 (in Bulgarian)
2. Pellaud B., Proliferation aspects of plutonium recycling, *Comptes Rendus Physique* **3.7** (2002) 1067-1079
3. Cacuci D.G. (ed.), Handbook of Nuclear Engineering, Vol. IV, Chapter 26, Springer, 2010
4. Bathke C.G. *et al.*, The Attractiveness of Materials in Advanced Fuel Cycles for Various Proliferation and Theft Scenarios, Los Alamos National Laboratory, LA-UR-10-00949, 2010
5. Bobrov E.A. *et al.*, Perspective closed fuel cycles based on REMIX technology in nuclear energy system with thermal and fast neutron reactors, *In: Neutronics-2012, Proceedings of Atomic Energy's Neutron-physical Problems 2012*, Obninsk, Russia, pp. 9-11, 2012 (in Russian)
6. Filipov K., I. Naydenov, Minor Actinides Production in Pressurised Water Reactors (III) – REMIX Fuel Usage, *In: Energy Forum 2017 Proceedings*, Varna, Bulgaria, 2017 (in press)
7. ORNL, Scale: A Comprehensive Modeling and Simulation Suite for Nuclear Safety Analysis and Design, ORNL/TM-2005/39, Version 6.1, June 2011

Authors:

Ivaylo Toshkov Naydenov, Assistant Professor, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, Technical University of Sofia, +359 898 597194, ivaylo.naydenov@gmail.com

Kalin Boyanov Filipov, PhD, Associated Professor, Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering, Technical University of Sofia, +359 (2) 965 2297, filipov@tu-sofia.bg